

Fire performance of a new shear transfer system for CFST columns

Minoo Ebrahimi ^{*, a}, Frederic Marimon ^a, Milad Soltanalipour ^a, Miquel Ferrer ^a
Felipe Álvarez ^b, Mar Alonso ^b, Juan José del Coz ^b, Juan Enrique Martínez ^b

^a Department of Strength of Materials and Structural Engineering,
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya BarcelonaTech (UPC), Spain
minoo.ebrahimi@upc.edu, frederic.marimon@upc.edu, milad.soltanalipour@upc.edu, miquel.ferrer@upc.edu

^b Departamento de Construcción e Ingeniería de Fabricación,
Universidad de Oviedo, Spain
felipe@constru.uniovi.es, mar@constru.uniovi.es, juanjo@constru.uniovi.es, quique@constru.uniovi.es

ABSTRACT

The conventional shear transfer elements applied in beam-to-CFST columns include shear studs, steel bars, angles, internal rings, and steel plates. The new UPCCFST system is comparatively easier to execute because the shear transfer elements are provided by simply punching the steel tube. In the first phase of the research, ambient temperature push-out tests were carried out involving 56 test specimens. The shear bond between the concrete core and the steel tube resulted up to 12.31 times greater than the plain CFST system. This paper studies the shear bond in UPCCFST columns exposed to extreme temperatures exceeding 500°. The testing procedure includes pre-loading at ambient temperature, applying a temperature curve up to 530°, and conducting a mechanical push-out test on a total number of 6 specimens. The results show that the average shear bond has improved by 2.08 times compared to the conventional flat CFST specimens. The failure modes, the force-slip relationship, and the concrete strength after the fire tests have also been analyzed. This research has been carried out through a collaboration between the Construction Engineering Area at the University of Oviedo and the Polytechnic University of Catalonia; under the competitive research project STCC SIFECAT: IU68009746, funded by European Regional Development Funds (ERDF) through Agència de Gestió d'Ajuts Universitaris i de Recerca (AGAUR) - Generalitat de Catalunya.

Keywords: CFST columns, Shear connection, Push-out test, Fire performance

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. State of the art

Concrete-Filled Steel Tube (CFST) has been extensively used in the construction sector due to its high strength, stiffness, exceptional seismic performance, ductility, and acceptable fire performance. Over the past few decades, significant research has been conducted to study the performance of CFST across a spectrum of environmental conditions: low, ambient, and high temperatures and post-fire scenarios with both experimental and numerical methods.

Despite the few studies on the fire performance of CFST columns (1; 2), the fire performance of Tubed Reinforced Concrete (TRC) columns has been the subject of several studies. These studies have analyzed thermal and deformation behaviors, axial stress, force, bending moment, working mechanism, and failure modes (3; 4). They have quantified the differences between isolated and TRC columns; and explored the complex effects of connected RC beams in square and rectangular columns (5). The results show that fire resistance decreases with increased load ratio and increases with

decreased sectional factor or dimension. A practical design method is proposed to determine fire resistance with or without fire protection. Several studies have been carried out to investigate the behavior of CFST after fire exposure (6), square reinforced concrete columns (7), and circular reinforced concrete columns (8; 9)

1.2. UPCCFST

UPCCFST is a new shear transfer system for square CFST columns. It is made up of protrusions on the steel sheet that are shaped as crowns and are orientated toward the side in contact with the concrete. It has strengthened the shear bond between the steel tube and the concrete core. The bond-slip behaviour of the UPCCFST system is ductile, whereas the failure of conventional CFST columns is brittle (10; 11). In addition, UPCCFST can lead to a faster construction, reduced material consumption, easier casting of columns without restricting the flow of fresh concrete, simplified joints, and economic and environmental benefits.

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

Table 1 shows the experimental campaign, which consists of six specimens. Three of them were made with punches, while the other three were without punches (flat steel tubes). The surface of the steel section in contact with the concrete is unpainted and free from oil, grease, and loose scale or rust according to Eurocode 4 (part 1–1 section 6.7.4.3) (12). The punch spacing is 40 mm (10).

Five K-type thermocouples were placed inside each specimen, at 350 mm height from the bottom in order to measure the temperature inside the concrete core. A block of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) with 50 mm depth was set in the lower part of the tube before casting, to allow the concrete to slip downwards inside the tube due to the loading. *Fig. 1* shows the location of the thermocouples and the lower EPS block inside the tubes before casting (left) and the specimens ready to test after concrete hardening (right).

Three standard cubic samples (150 mm) were used for the concrete compression tests. A characteristic mean value of $f_{ck} = 22.6 \text{ MPa}$ was obtained from the testing. *Table 2* shows the concrete strength test results, according to UNE-EN 12390-3 (2020). The characteristic strength was calculated according to the Spanish standard EHE-08.

Table 1 Summary of specimens and properties

Specimen	Bonding system	Total length L_t [mm]	Steel thickness t [mm]	Width B [mm]
Flat-01	Flat	600	4	200
Flat-02	Flat	600	4	200
Flat-03	Flat	600	4	200
Punch-01	UPC patent	600	4	200
Punch-02	UPC patent	600	4	200
Punch-03	UPC patent	600	4	200

Table 2 Concrete strength test results

Specimen	Density [kg/m ³]	Load [kN]	Strength [MPa]
1	2331	761.7	33.9
2	2350	760.6	33.8
3	2405	768.7	34.2
Mean value	2362	763.67	34.0
		Cylinder conversion (x0.9):	30.6
		Characteristic strength (-8 MPa):	22.6

Fig. 1 Thermocouples setting up (left) and specimens ready for testing (right)

2.1. Test Equipment

2.1.1. Furnace for fire resistance testing

The furnace used for thermal and thermo-mechanical tests includes a thermal chamber, fumes extraction system, a PID controller and a loading mobile frame. The PID controller operates three high-speed diesel burners independently, while the mobile frame has a hydraulic actuator for vertical load application during the thermo-mechanical test. In order to apply the load on the specimen inside the furnace, it is necessary to use a cooled extension on the actuator (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 a) Furnace; b) Actuator; c) Cooled extension

2.1.2. Measure equipment

Four plate thermometers are used to measure bulk temperature inside the furnace, 450 mm away from any surface, according to UNE-EN 1363-1 (Fig. 3.a). The plate thermometers in Fig. 4.a) were rotated 90° to place them parallel to the CSFT exposed surface. The loading system consists of a hydraulic group and jack with a loading capacity of 750 kN. The actuator is powered by a data acquisition unit and Wintest 32 control software, enabling the application of both constant and variable loads. Two displacement transducers were used to measure the relative vertical displacement of concrete to the steel tube (Fig. 3.b). An impact sclerometer was used to measure the surface concrete strength after the fire tests.

Fig. 3a) Plate thermometers inside the furnace (UNE-EN 1363-1); b) Displacement transducers 1363-1

2.2. Test procedure

First, the specimen is placed on its support and the thermocouple wires are driven out through the hole at the center of the supporting plate. To prevent buckling phenomena during the loading an 18 mm thick steel plate (shown in gray in Fig. 4.a) was placed at the center of the support. The specimen support was then protected by adding several layers of high-temperature resistant mineral wool. The upper side of the furnace was then sealed, and the loading elements were placed on the top of the specimen together with the load actuator as shown in (Fig. 4.b).

Fig. 4 a) Setting up the test specimen; b) Actuator and loading frame

Two pre-loading stages are carried out at ambient temperature to crush the ceramic wool used to insulate so that unrealistic displacement values can be avoided. The first pre-load stage consists of ramps up to 10, 15, 20, and 25 kN (Fig. 5.a). In the second stage, a constant speed load increment of 0.15 kN/s is applied up to 25 kN (Fig. 5.b).

Fig. 5 Pre-loading stages time-histories: a) Ramped; b) Constant speed

The Temperature-Time curves related to the thermocouples embedded in the concrete core are shown in Fig. 6.a . The test started by heating the specimens for 4 hours. At the minute 110, two cells of the burners failed, the test was stopped and the cells were replaced. The rest was resumed at minute 160 until the mean temperature in the thermocouple located at the center of the concrete core (TC3) was between 530 and 580°C.

Once the temperature of the inner thermocouples was similar (TC2, TC3 and TC4 to 562.34 °C) the mechanical test was started by applying a vertical load, following rate of 10 kN/min (TEST1). At the end (approaching 224 kN), there was no slip between the concrete and the steel and a displacement of 8.72 mm was reached. A second test was carried out after 15 minutes, with a loading rate of 20 kN/min (TEST2).

Fig. 6.b shows the specimen during and after the test. No significant cracks were observed, and the slip produced during the test was almost recovered after the test, as the measured position differences were smaller than 1 mm.

Fig. 6 a) Measured temperatures over time; b) Specimen during and after the test

3. TEST RESULTS

3.1. Shear bond strength

The shear bond strength between the concrete core and the steel tube is defined using the following equation.

$$\tau = \frac{F}{4(B - 2t)L} \quad (1)$$

Where, F is the push force, B width, t thickness and L the shear length. Table 3 shows the average shear bond strengths and their standard deviations (SD).

Table 3 Shear bond strengths and Standard Deviations (SD)

ID	Bonding system	A [mm ²]	F [kN]	τ [N/mm ²]	τ_{Ave} [N/mm ²]	SD [N/mm ²]
Flat-01	Flat	422400	69	0.16		
Flat-02	Flat	422400	45	0.11	0.1333	0.0252
Flat-03	Flat	422400	55	0.13		
Punch-01	Punched	422400	119	0.28		
Punch-02	Punched	422400	115	0.27	0.2750	0.0071

The Punch-03 test result has been excluded from the average shear bond strength.

3.2. Slip

Table 4 shows the first, final and average slip loads of the tested specimens.

Table 4 First and the final slip loads

ID	First Slip Load [kN]	Slip [mm]	Final Slip Load [kN]	Average Slip Load [kN]
Flat-01*	17 (ambient) 69 (furnace)	11 11	69	
Flat-02*	12 (furnace) 45 (furnace)	8 13	45	56.33
Flat-03	55 (furnace)	18	55	
Punch-01	119	22	119	
Punch-02	115	22	115	117

*Two resistant stages: chemical bond + slip friction.

3.2.1. Result of Flat CFST tests

Flat-01: A slip value of 11 mm was produced during the pre-loading stage, being 17 kN of the applied load. The force-slip relationship is linear until the force reaches 69 kN (Fig. 7). **Flat -02:** The first slip is produced at 8 mm. The force-slip relationship is linear until 45 kN, when an abrupt slip of 2 mm is produced. The loading rate was kept until 120 kN, with a corresponding total slip value of 18 mm (Fig. 8). **Flat-03:** At 55 kN, the first slip occurs, reaching 17 mm. Eventually, the load was increased until 95 kN, and the slip increased up to 19 mm (Fig. 9).

Fig. 7 a) Registered temperatures during the test; b) Loading rate and Slip [S] - Force [F] relationship (Flat-01)

Fig. 8 a) Registered temperatures during the test; b) Loading rate and Slip [S] - Force [F] relationship (Flat-02)

Fig. 9 a) Registered temperatures during the test; b) Loading rate and Slip [S] - Force [F] relationship (Flat-03)

3.2.2. Result of Punched CFST tests

Punch-01: The slip-force relationship is linear up to 100 kN. Then, the slip increases until 22 mm and the load up to 119 kN (Fig. 10). **Punch-02:** The slip-force relationship was linear until 90 kN, then exponential until 115 kN, reaching a slip of 21 mm (Fig. 11).

Fig. 10 a) Registered temperatures during the test; b) Loading rate and Slip [S]- Force [F] relationship (Punch-01)

Fig. 11 a) Registered temperatures during the test; b) Loading rate and Slip [S] - Force [F] relationship (Punch-02)

3.3. Concrete surface strength after fire tests

After test, the steel tube was cut and the concrete of specimens Flat-02 and Punch-02 was tested at the surface using an impact sclerometer, according to UNE-EN 12504-2. The concrete samples were mapped into an 18 squared mesh. The average strength value of these tests was 20.89 MPa. The concrete strength after fire tests is 31.7% lower than the strength of the original concrete compression tests of the cubic samples (30.6 MPa). The compression resistance characteristic value is also 7.5% lower (22.6 MPa). *Table 5* shows the experimental values of these tests.

Table 5 Concrete surface strength after fire test measured with an impact sclerometer device

ID	Punch-02		Flat-02	
	Rebound Index	Surface strength [MPa]	Rebound Index	Surface strength [MPa]
1	22	18	26	23
2	27	25	26	23
3	27	25	26	23
4	26	23	26	23
5	27	25	24	20
6	26	23	24	20
7	26	23	24	20
8	24	20	25	22
9	22	18	28	26
10	26	23	24	20
11	25	22	20	15
12	27	25	20	15
13	28	26	22	18
14	28	26	21	16
15	26	23	25	22
16	21	16	22	18
17	23	19	20	15
18	20	15	22	18
Average		21.94		19.83

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

4.1. Slip comparison between the Flat and Punched CFSTs

In all specimens, the slip progressed until reaching the maximum load. Additionally, no cracks or damage were observed in the concrete core of the flat specimens after the fire tests. Upon extracting the specimen Punch-02, a curvature is observed in the lower section of the tube. This is due to the gradual increase in load from 119 to 209 kN in the end of test, resulting in a final displacement of 22 mm. The steel tube was cut to identify if the concrete had been crushed and to inspect the condition of the steel punches. Only small amounts of detached concrete were found at the corners of the tube. None of the punches on the inner side of the tube were visibly deformed, and the concrete remained attached to the tube on four edges. Therefore, it can be concluded that the slip was caused by concrete failure rather than punch failure, despite the steel temperature was over 500°C during the test.

4.2. Slip-Force comparison between the Flat and Punched CFSTs

The slip of punched specimens under fire action is produced gradually, increasing the slope until the test is completed. This is in contrast with the behavior of flat specimens, whose first slip is produced abruptly when the force is high enough to break the initial adherence between the steel-concrete interface.

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